

Evolution of the Exoskeleton- IIT Delhi

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Abstract— This paper proposes the evolution of the development of the exoskeleton. In this regard, all the versions of the exoskeleton have been discussed in this paper [version 1 to version 4]. An issue regarding the exoskeleton, which is being used for tele-operating the KUKA-KR5 manipulator, is also discussed. Switching of communication from TCP/IP to UDP protocol is also discussed. Implementation of I2C protocol rather than using a mesh of wires is also discussed. In order to remove the noise, the 4th order butter worth filter in hardware and median filter in software is also implemented. PMB brakes are also implemented in the exoskeleton in order to have the haptic feedback and can avoid the collision of the KUKA while performing tele-operation. Integration of the Exoskeleton with the immersive environment for visual feedback to perform the Peg-in-hole operation is also discussed. The pros and Cons of each version of the exoskeleton are also discussed. Finally, experimental results are presented to support the approach in this paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

In tele-operation operating a machine at a distance is performed. Real-time situations like disasters or space applications in which the environment is hazardous to human beings. In these types of situations, it is expedient to deploy robots to prevent human loss. As human operators from a safe location control the robot's motion, i.e., have distance from radiation and chemicals affected area. This overall architecture requires a sound level of cooperation between the wearer and robots. To overcome the communication lag, the use of a portable device having the feature of force-feedback is incorporated. This paper introduces various versions of the exoskeleton that evolves in time with various extended features accompanied by the grace of time.

The basic purpose design of the exoskeleton is to allow a human operator wearing an exoskeleton-based haptic interface for the human arm to remotely control a virtual slave robot. It is composed of various electrical, electronic and software components that enable us to do the tele-operation in an effective and efficient manner.

A. Exoskeleton Version 1 (EXO V1)

In tele-operation operating a machine at a distance is performed. We develop an Arm Exoskeleton. This exoskeleton comprises 7 joints and is used for tele-operation with the KUKA KR5 industrial manipulator. As Kuka has 6 joints and Exo has 7 joints. We perform forward kinematics of the exoskeleton and send the ExoX, ExoY, ExoZ, to the Kuka, as joint-to-joint mapping is feasible in this tele-operation process.

The development of the exoskeleton is evolved in order to perform inserting the peg in a hole. So, in order to reach this task to perform in a nuclear reactor area where human intervention is hazardous to human health, we have to take care of each and every module of the exoskeleton which is running in a real-time scenario, as there have been

successful implementations of the human arm exoskeleton [1, 2, 3, and 4]. In the entire human arm discussed, the controlling device may be a joystick, a mouse, or a steering wheel. The exoskeleton version 1 was developed in our lab, as shown in Figure. 1. Various attempts have been performed in order to measure arm movements without an exoskeleton, but such an approach fails to provide a feedback system [5].

Figure 1. Exoskeleton Version I

A.1 Kinematic Design of Exoskeleton Version 1

The exoskeleton, which has been developed as shown in (Fig. 1) is to be worn by a human operator and controls an industrial robot through their hand motion. The KUKA KR5 is a six-degree of freedom (DOF) manipulator, whereas the human arm, and correspondingly the anthropometric exoskeleton (shown schematically in Figure 2), has seven DOFs. There are three degrees of freedom at the shoulder joint, two at the elbow joint and two at the wrist. Rotational sensors are mounted on seven different joints on the exoskeleton to sense the joint angles' variations.

Figure 2. An exoskeleton robot to be worn on human arm (Version1)

A.2 Hardware and Software Interfacing

PCB design for the new pots and filter: Double layer PCB has been design to make it compact as shown in fig. 3.

Figure 3. NI circuit CAD model of PCB for pots

Tele-operation implies operation from a distance. Figure 4 shows one such scenario. Two systems one connected to Exoskeleton and the other to virtual KUKA manipulator are coherent in the task space. These two systems have been kept separated between two labs in our department.

Figure 4. Remotely controlling Exoskeleton and virtual KUKA

In order to verify the mapping of Exo -Kuka, we have made a separate application. In contrast to our tele-operation application, we must manually feed the Exo Joint angles. The application presents both the Exo and KUKA manipulator models side by side. Each iteration of the Exo Joint angle is reflected in its model along with the corresponding state of the Kuka model. This application can discern errors arising from the Exo with those inherent within our tele-operation Code. Figure 5 shows the application windows. Windows form at the lower right corner contains several buttons that either increment or decrement each of the seven Exo joint angles. Whereas the 'Reset' button brings the Exo position to that which a human arm attains once it is lowered straight.

B. Exoskeleton Version 2 (EXO V2)

In exoskeleton version 2 many drawbacks of previous versions have been rectified and are discussed in this section. Exoskeleton version 2 is shown in figure 6 below.

Figure 5. Manual input to exoskeleton for KUKA replication for debugging

Figure 6. Exoskeleton Version 2

B.1 Kinematic Design of Exoskeleton Version 2

A CAD model of the exoskeleton was made by Autodesk's inventor, and various ergonomic aspects to its design were looked into to remove deficiencies seen in the earlier version. After several CAD iterations, arm geometry consistent with upper arm goniometry was achieved. Static analysis using the Finite Element modeling package was used to compute the maximum deflection and used to drive the design of link elements.

Figure 7. An exoskeleton robot to be worn on human arm (Version 2)

B.2 Design of Compliant Cantilever

Links have sensors and feedback brakes, and misalignment prevailing between them causes damages and poor results. To reduce misalignment, we have designed a compliant cantilever structure, as shown in Fig. 8, which is stiff about the rotation axis and flexible about other axes. For analysis, we have done finite element analysis Using Ansys APDL. Figure 9 depicts torsional stiffness about three axes for 0.5 mm in thickness (sheet). This concludes that the cantilever complies with the rotation axis. Using a compliant cantilever, we have made an assembly of SRACM modeled in Autodesk inventor as shown in Fig. 10 where brake and link are connected by compliant cantilever similarly potentiometer and link is also connected to compensate misalignment between them.

Figure 8. Ansys APDL mesh model of compliant cantilever for SRACM

Figure 9: Torsional stiffness for a sheet thickness of 0.5 mm

Figure 10. Arrangement of Brake, potentiometer and links with flexible cantilever

B.3 Implementation of brakes in three joints for haptic feedback to avoid collision

Haptics refers to sensing and manipulation through touch. The three brakes incorporated in exoskeleton as shown in figure 6. Brake has been incorporated for haptic feedback in the system. The three brakes were considered, one is placed on elbow and other two on wrist. The compliant cantilever shown in Figure 10 is used as coupling to transfer motion between the brake and the link. One end of the cantilever is connected to link and the end is connected to the brake axis.

The function of the compliant cantilever here is to overcome any misalignment that is present between the axis of the link joint and the brake. This customized cantilever is compliant about five DOF allowing the sixth DOF to transfer the load. The load from the link is transferred through this axis to the brake. The similar compliant system design is also made to avoid the misalignment in sensors [6].

B.4 Implementation of I2C protocol

Our investigation of the noise related problems with the previous versions of exoskeleton necessitated the introduction of the analogue to digital converters (ADC's). Two ADC's were introduced within the exoskeleton system. The signals from three shoulder joints are connected the first ADC₁ and the signals from the three wrist along with the elbow joints is connected to second ADC₂. The use of ADC's allowed the system to be less prone to the noise.

The brakes connected to the exoskeleton, in order to implement haptics interface, were also connected to the I2C bus. A USB to I2C convertor is used to interface the exoskeleton data acquisition circuit to the host computer. A custom application using the MS Visual C#.NET language was developed. The BOURNS 3382 potentiometer is connected at every individual joint of exoskeleton. The data from the potentiometer are sent to the respective ADC devices. The output from these ADC devices is fed to the I2C to USB device. Fig. 11 shows the block diagram of the I2C implementation in the exoskeleton. The data from the I2C master device is fed to the console application running on the host computer via USB. Further the data from the host computer is sent to the connect KUKA KR5.

Fig. 11. Block Diagram of I2C implementation in Exoskeleton

The data transfer rate depends on crystal frequency of slave controller. Fig. 12 shows a typical arrangement of I2C communication in exoskeleton robot.

Fig.12. A typical I2C protocol

C. Exoskeleton Version 3 (EXO V3)

In exoskeleton version 3 many drawbacks of previous versions has been rectified and are discussed in this section. Exoskeleton version 3 is shown in figure 13.

Figure 13. An arm exoskeleton worn by an operator.

C.1 Implementation of Butterworth Filter and Median Filter

Butterworth filter is implemented. It is a type of signal processing filter, designed to have as flat a frequency response as possible in the pass-band [7]. The frequency response of the Butterworth filter is maximally flat (i.e. has no ripples) in the.

pass-band and rolls off towards zero in the stop-band. Butterworth filter was implemented in order to filter the output signal generated from all the seven individual joints of the exo-skeleton as shown in figure 14. The median filter is normally used to reduce noise in a signal, somewhat like the mean filter [8-10].

Fig. 14. Hardware of 4th order butterworth filter

C.2 Immersive Environment Interaction (Real, Augmented Reality Environment KUKA and Real Exo-station)

We have developed a separate application to interface with the exoskeleton [11-13]. The exo-station application determines mapping between the six angles of the Kuka and the seven angles of the exo-station. Then it sends the calculated values of the six angles, using these we animate the model of the Kuka in our application as shown in fig. 15.

Fig. 15 (a, b, c, d) [a-b: Kuka moving upward in Real and Immersive, Exo-station is moving upward], [c-d: Kuka moving in -Y direction in Real and Immersive, Exo-station is moving in -Y direction].

C.3. Communication flow between Exoskeleton, Immersive Environment and KUKA

Integration between Exoskeleton, Virtual KUKA, Immersive Environment and Real KUKA: For integration between the systems, UDP is used to transmit data between computers, as one computer is connected to Exoskeleton and other computers connected to respective systems for the integration. The layout is illustrated in fig.16. The data structure that is being transmitted between the computers shown in fig.17.

Fig. 16. TCP and UDP communication between Force, Exoskeleton, Immersive Environment.

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Data Structure:
enum source
{
Force, Exo;
}
float angle1, angle2, angle3;
float angle4, angle5, angle6;
float kuka X, kuka Y, kuka Z;
float kuka A, kuka B, kuka C;
float force X, forceY, force Z;

```

Fig. 17. Data structure transmitted between the sub systems.

D. Exoskeleton Version 4 (EXO V4)

In this section various features that is included in this new version of exoskeleton [version 4] is discussed.

- D.1 Removal of Brakes from wrist area
- D.2 Shifting of Wrist Roll Sensor towards Elbow Joint area
- D.3 Modular fitment for sensors and accompanying electronics
- D.4 Body Strap Attachment
- D.5 Stick Joystick Design
- D.6 Improved Ergonomics

This version of exoskeleton is in the manufacturing phase. The CAD model of exoskeleton version 4 is shown in figure 18.

II. CONTROL SYSTEM

In this section control algorithm for tele-operation with the KUKA robot via Immersive environment is discussed. Control algorithm execution is controlled by the three switches [Switch1, Switch2, and Switch3]. Switch1 is used for triggering and send the velocity values in each axes of the end effector from exoskeleton to the Kuka and updating the joint angles taking as feedback from Kuka to the Immersive environment. As the operator is doing tele-operation for peg in hole insertion by seeing the visuals of immersive environment.

Fig. 18. CAD Model of Exoskeleton version 4.

Fig. 19. Flow Control of the System Architecture

When we reach to the vicinity of the hole then Switch2 is pressed in order to have less scaling factor [0.6] for higher precision. After attaining high precision locking of the exoskeleton [other than 3 wrist joints] is performed.

Switch3 is triggered for opening and closing of the gripper by setting bool flag [GB1, GB2] in the control algorithm. As flag value changes after the insertion we unlock the joints [Joint0-Joint3] and stop the control algorithm. The implementation of algorithm discussed above is shown in fig 19 below.

III. TELE-OPERATION PERFORMANCE

A. Exoskeleton [Joint0-Joint6]

Fig. 20. Theta values of each joint [joint0-joint6] of Exo-station.

Fig.20 shows that the theta values of all joint of exoskeleton has been recorded and all the values are independent from each other. Theta0, Theta1, and Theta2 show the shoulder joint. Range of flexion and extension of each joints 180, 90 and 220 degrees. Theta 3 is for elbow motion and range is 180 degrees. Wrist joint also have three joint angles. The range of Theta4, theta5, and theta6 are 150, 70 and 90.

B. Exostation [ExoX, ExoY, ExoZ]

Fig. 21. [ExoX, ExoY, ExoZ] values of the exo-station after performing forward kinematics.

C. Exoskeleton – KUKA mapping

Fig. 22. Exoskeleton and KUKA mapping in X axis.

Fig. 23. Exoskeleton and KUKA mapping in Y axis.

Fig. 24. Exoskeleton and KUKA mapping in Z axis.

Filters of this class are generally specified by two parameters, the filter order and the cutoff frequency. The frequency response is monotonic, and the filter order dictates the sharpness of the transition from the pass band to the stop band. 4th order low pass Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 2 Hz was designed for every individual joint of the exoskeleton.

IV. COMPARISON TABLE

Table 1: Shows the comparison table of different versions of exoskeleton. [Version 4* : In Manufacturing Stage]

Features	Version 1	Version 2	Version 3	Version 4*
Goniometry	7 Joints	7 Joints	7 Joints	7 Joints
Kinematics	D-H Table	D-H change	D-H change	D-H change
Interface	Exo-Virtual Kuka	Exo-Real Kuka	Exo-Kuka-Immersive kuka	do
Electronic Component	7 POT + DAC card + 1 Switch	7 [Bourns Rot. Sensor]	Adding I2C + butterworth filter + 3 Switches	do
Haptics	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Communication protocols	TCP/IP	TCP/IP + UDP	TCP/IP + UDP	TCP/IP + UDP

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